
SELF- REGULATED LEARNING (SRL) AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**Dr. Kamlesh Dhull***Assistant Professor, Vaish College of Education, Rohtak.*

ABSTRACT

The present study is an attempt to find out the impact of self-regulated learning on academic achievement of senior secondary school students. A sample of 150 students studying in of 11th and 12th class selected randomly from two schools of Rohtak city. Test of Self-Regulated Learning Scale by Gupta and Mehtani was used to collect the data. Academic achievement of the students was determined on the basis of marks obtained in previous class (10th Class marks). Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' test was used to analyse the data. The findings of the study revealed that academic achievement score of students belonging to high self-regulated learning group is higher than mean academic achievement score of students belonging to moderate and low self regulatory learning group, while academic achievement score of students belonging to moderate self-regulated learning group is higher than mean academic achievement score of students belonging to low self regulatory learning group.

Key words: *Self regulated learning, academic achievement, senior secondary school students*

INTRODUCTION

Educational researchers have begun recently to identify and study key processes through which students self-regulate their academic learning. In this overview, it represents a general definition of self-regulated academic learning and identifies the distinctive features of their capability for acquiring knowledge and skill. It discusses how the study of component processes contributes to our growing understanding of the distinctive features of students' self-regulated learning. Finally, the implications of self-regulated learning perspective on students' learning and achievement are considered.

At one time or another, we all have observed self-regulated learners. They approach educational tasks with confidence, diligence, and resourcefulness. Perhaps most importantly, self-regulated learners are aware when they know a fact or possess a skill and when they do not. Unlike their passive classmates, self-regulated students proactively seek out information when needed and take the necessary steps to master it. When they encounter obstacles such as poor study conditions, confusing teachers, or abstruse text books, they find a way to succeed. Self-regulated learners view acquisition as a systematic and controllable process, and they accept greater responsibility for their achievement outcomes (see Borkowski, Carr, Rellinger, & Pressley, in press; Zimmerman & Martinez-Pons, 1990).

Self-Regulation is not a mental ability or an academic performance skill: rather it is the self- directive process by which learning transform their mental abilities into academic skills. Learning is viewed as an activity that students do for them-selves in a proactive way rather than as a covert event that happens to them in reaction to teaching. Self-regulation refers to self-generated thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that are oriented to attaining goals (Zimmerman, 2000). These learners are proactive in their efforts to learn because they are aware of their strengths and limitations and because they are guided by personally set goals and task- related strategies. Such as using an arithmetic addition strategy to check the accuracy of solutions to subtraction problems. These learners monitor their behavior in terms of their goals and self- reflect on their increasing effectiveness. This enhances their self- satisfaction and motivation to continue to improve their

methods of learning. Because of their superior motivation and adaptive learning methods, self-regulated students are not only more likely to succeed academically but to view their futures optimistically.

Self-regulation is important because a major function of education is the development of lifelong learning skills. After graduation from high school or college, young adults must learn many important skills informally. For example, in business settings, they are often expected to learn a new position, such as selling a product, by observing proficient others and by practicing on their own. Those who develop high levels of skill position themselves for bonuses, early promotion, or more attractive jobs. In self-employment settings, both young and old must constantly self-refine their skills in order to survive. Their capability to self-regulate is especially challenged when they undertake long-term creative projects, such as works of art, literary texts, or inventions. In recreational settings, learners spend much personally regulated time learning diverse skills for self-entertainment, ranging from hobbies to sports.

Self-regulated learners exercise effort regulation, which is construed as students' intentions to put forth resources, energy, and time not secure completion of important academic tasks (Pintrich and others, 1993). Skilled self-regulated learners are those who generate extraordinary motivational beliefs in order to secure goal accomplishments. They are also those who, when conflicts arise between pursuing important academic goals and alternative tempting options, learn how to remain task-focused despite immediate impulses to succumb to attractive temptations.

Zimmerman (1990) reveals that Benjamin Franklin wrote extensively about techniques he used to improve his learning, erudition and self-control. Franklin detailed how he set learning goals for himself, and he consciously selected exemplary written models to improve his writing. As Zimmerman states, Franklin's use of these procedures is an indication that self-regulation has been deemed important for a very long time.

Importance of Self-Regulation Strategies-

There is evidence to support the notion that training in certain self-regulation strategies enhance school achievement and performance. A research study carried out by Camahalan (2006), involved a specific Self-Regulated Learning Programme consisting of four main components, one of which was to explicitly instruct students in self-regulated learning strategies. They included 14 self-regulated learning strategies derived from Zimmerman's Social Cognitive Theory (1989). The purpose of each strategy was to improve students' self-regulation of their personal functioning, academic behavioral performance, and learning environment. Strategies included goal – setting and planning, self-evaluation and seeking information. Camahalan concluded that self-regulated learning strategy instruction engaged students' involvement and interest and gave them the opportunity to monitor and evaluate progress of their work: set goals and plan for activities: as well as select or arrange the physical environment to make learning easier.

Academic Achievement

The development of a Country relies mostly on the levels of education among the people. Education is a process towards development. Academic achievement refers to what and how an individual has learnt qualitatively and quantitatively after a period of instruction given. Academic Achievement can be described as successful accomplishments in a particular subject's area usually by reasons of skills, hard work, scores or descriptive commentary. School achievement may be affected by different factors like study habits, intelligence and attitudes of learners towards school, socioeconomic status and different aspects of their personality etc.

Academic achievement means the achievement level of students. It helps in declaring students successful or unsuccessful, choosing students for various courses and selecting students for different jobs. It is the level of learning in a particular area of subject in terms of knowledge, understanding, skill and application usually

evaluated by teachers in the form of test scores in their examination. Good (1973), defined academic achievement as, "knowledge attained or skills developed in the school subjects, usually designated by test scores or by marks assigned by teachers, or by both."

Academic achievement among secondary school students in relation to area mechanism through which adolescents learn about their talents, abilities and competencies which are an important part of developing career aspirations (Lent, Brown, & Hackett, 2000). Academic achievement of students is affected by many factors that may reduce it; academic anxiety is one of them. Whether the performance of high academic anxiety group of learners is different from the low academic anxiety group of learners, this study will try to unearth this fact. In this study the term academic achievement has been taken as the performance of learners after a course and is measured in terms of marks obtained by the students.

Self-regulated learning theories of academic achievement are distinctive from other accounts of learning and instruction by their emphasis (a) on how students select, organize, or create advantageous learning environments for themselves and (b) on how they plan and control the form and amount of their own instruction. Undoubtedly, all learners are responsive to some degree during instruction; however, students who display initiative, intrinsic motivation and personal responsibility achieve particular academic success (Zimmerman & Martinez-Pons, 1988). These self-regulated students are distinguished by their systematic use of metacognitive, motivational, and behavioral strategies; by their responsiveness to feedback regarding the effectiveness of their learning; and by their self-perceptions of academic accomplishment.

Contributors to this issue of the Educational Psychologist review and analyze recent research and theory on key self-regulatory processes students use to learn and achieve academically. Our understanding of the interdependence of these processes has now reached the point where systematic efforts can be launched to teach self-regulation to students who approach learning passively, and a number of notable efforts have been undertaken already (see Graham & Harris, 1989; Weinstein & Mayer, 1986). Existing laboratory training studies caution, however, that limited attempts at instruction that focus on only one or two processes are unlikely to promote long-term effects. Instead, attention must be directed toward developing all three dimensions of self-regulated learning in students: metacognitive, motivational, and behavioral. At a time when students often appear to lack both the will and skill to achieve academically, educators need instructional approaches that can offer direction and insight into the processes of self-regulated learning.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Eisenbergin (2010) stated that for internalizing problems are less consistent and robust, although emotion-related self regulation appears to be inversely related to internalizing problems after the early years. Self-regulatory capacities have been related to both genetic and environmental factors and their interaction. Some interventions designed to foster self regulation and, hence, reduce maladjustment, have proved to be at least partially effective. **Shea and Bidjerano (2010)** conclude that a positive relationship exists between elements of the CoI framework and between elements of a nascent theoretical construct that label learning presence. They suggest that learning presence represents elements such as self- efficacy as well as other cognitive, behavioral, and motivational constructs supportive of online learner self regulation. **McAuley et al. (2011)** showed significant direct effects of two elements of executive function and of strategy use on self efficacy and of efficacy on adherence. In addition, there were significant indirect effects of strategy use and executive function on adherence via self efficacy. Higher levels of executive function and use of self-regulatory strategies at the start of an exercise program enhance beliefs in exercise capabilities, which in turn leads to greater adherence. Banajee and Kumar (2014) revealed that SRL is moderately positive correlated with academic achievement. At different dimensions of the SRL, male and female science graduate students

do not differ significantly but at environment they differ significantly. The Implications are presented in the article. **Mahmoodi, Kalantarib and Ghaslani (2014)** found a significant relationship between motivation and self regulated learning, there was no significant relationship between self regulated learning and L2 achievement. Cetin (2015) showed that there was no correlation between GPA and academic motivation and academic self-regulation learning. In other words, the students' academic motivation and academic self-regulated learning total scores, together, did not predict their GPA. San, **Roslan, and Sabouripour (2016)** revealed intrinsic goal orientation, task values, rehearsal, elaboration, meta cognitive self-regulation, resource management strategies, organisation and critical thinking as self-regulated learning components that have significant negative correlations with academic procrastination. In addition, anxiety was found to have a significant positive correlation with academic procrastination. Extrinsic goal orientation and control of learning beliefs were not significantly correlated to academic procrastination. **Alotaibi, Tohmaz, and Jabak (2017)** indicated that the study instrument was valid and reliable for use in a Saudi university environment. Furthermore, results indicated that there is a significant and positive relationship between self-regulated learning and the academic achievement of students.

Justification of the Study

Self-Regulated Learners are cognizant of their academic strengths and weaknesses and they have a repertoire of strategies- they appropriately apply to tackle the day- to- day challenges of academic task. Finally, students who are self- regulated learners believe that opportunities to take on challenging task practice their learning, develop a deep understanding of subject matter, and exert effort will give rise to academic success. All these characteristics may help to explain why self- regulated learners usually exhibit a high sense of self efficiency, high level of achievement, self confidence, self esteem etc. Review of students exhibits that student's academic achievement motivational beliefs, personality, and overall well- being is highly related with self regulated learning.

Today is the age of competitions and excel in their studies. everywhere; we find cut throat competition in all fields. So students have to give their best. Today most of the students study under the guidance their teachers. No doubt, some of them became good achiever but Along with teacher's guidance, students must be self- regulated in his/her learning. Self awareness, planning, self- motivation, self evaluation and self modification are some characteristics of a self- regularized student. No doubt, if a student's has some of these characteristics, he/she must be a good achiever. Keeping all these facts, investigator decided to study the variable self- regulated learning and its effect on academic achievement.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:-

“SELF- REGULATED LEARNING (SRL) AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS”

OBJECTIVE:

1. To study the effect of SRL on academic achievement of senior secondary school students

HYPOTHESIS:

1. There will be no significant effect of Self- Regulated Learning (SRL) on academic achievement of senior secondary school students

METHOD OF THE STUDY

The normative survey method was used to study the problem referring to the comparative study of study habits of male and female students of government and private schools.

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

Students studying in secondary schools constituted the target population of the present study. The total sample for the study comprises of 150 students of 11th and 12th class selected randomly from two schools. The schools included in the sample are located in Rohtak city.

TOOL USED

1. Test of Self-Regulated Learning Scale by Gupta and Mehtani was used.
2. Academic achievement of the students was determined on the basis of marks obtained in previous class (10th Class marks).

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Descriptive statistics such as Mean, S.D. and 't' test were worked out on the scores of self-regulated learning.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

The first objective of the investigation was to study the effect of self regulated learning on academic achievement of senior secondary school students. To attain this objective Mean S.D and 't' test was applied and have been reported in table no. 1.

Table 1

Statistical analysis of mean of academic achievement of students in high moderate and low self-regulated learning

Self-Regulated Learning	No. of student	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of significance
HSRL	35	72.75	9.37	13.47*	significant
LSRL	45	50.89	13.25		
HSRL	35	72.75	9.37	2.83*	Significant
MSRL	70	68.88	9.92		
LSRL	45	50.89	13.25	10.87*	Significant
MSRL	70	68.88	9.92		

Note:

HSRL-High self-regulated learning

MSRL-Moderate self-regulated learning

LSRL-Low self-regulated learning

The table 1 shows that the computed 't' value (13.47) for the difference between mean scores of academic achievement the two groups was found significant at the 0.01 level of significance. It shows that there is a significant difference between high and low self regulated learning students. It is clear that mean academic achievement score of HSRL group is higher that mean academic achievement score of LSRL group students. The table further shows that the computed 't' value (2.83) for the difference between mean scores of academic achievement the two groups was found significant at the 0.01 level of significance. It shows that there is a significant difference between high and moderate self regulated learning students. It is clear that mean academic achievement score of HSRL group is higher that mean academic achievement score of MSRL group students. The last part of the table shows that the computed 't' value (10.87) for the difference between mean scores of academic achievement the two groups was found significant at the 0.01 level of significance. It shows that there is a significant difference between low and moderate self regulated learning students. It is clear that mean academic achievement score of LSRL group is higher that mean academic achievement score of MSRL group students. Hence, the null hypothesis framed earlier, "There will be no

significant effect of Self- Regulated Learning (SRL) on academic achievement of senior secondary school students” is not retained.

MAIN FINDINGS

- 1. It was found that academic achievement score of students belonged to high self-regulated learning group is higher than mean academic achievement score of students belonged to low self regulatory learning group.**
- 2. It was found that academic achievement score of students belonged to high self-regulated learning group is higher than mean academic achievement score of students belonged to moderate self regulatory learning group.**
- 3. It was found that academic achievement score of students belonged to moderate self-regulated learning group is higher than mean academic achievement score of students belonged to low self regulatory learning group.**

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Self-regulation of learning occupies a fundamental place in postsecondary education. It is hard to think about the academic success of students in our colleges and universities if the students are not self – directed and self-motivated and cannot sustain cognition, affect, and behavior in order to assist in pursuing their academic and professional goals. The self-regulated learning makes changes in academic achievement among the senior secondary students. We can say that a person who possesses the self-regulated learning will also achieve more in his/her academic activities more over the self-regulated learning is an increasing- factor of academic achievement. Now a day’s education is mainly based on the academic marks of the students at all level. The good academic achievement is also depends on the aspect of SRL so students would focus on their self-motivation and Meta cognition development and reforming in their behavior as well as their evaluation. One can improve his academic performance by possessing the good level of SRL throughout his entire life. There for it can be enlighten the future of and individual.

This study is also helpful for the student effectively. Creating SRL Environment for the complex and divers range of backgrounds skill sets, and personalities that many students encompass poses challenges to even the most experienced teachers fortunately a great deal of literature show cases a variety of effective instructional strategic for encouraging self-regulation in the class room some of these strategic include direct instruction and modeling guided and independent practice, and reflective practice.

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